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**Davlatova Dilrabo,
Usmanova Shoira**
Tashkent Medical Academy
Tashkent State Dental Institute
shoira.usmanova.1980@gmail.com

THE ROLE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Numerous studies have proven that endothelial dysfunction in periodontal tissues often leads to the formation of chronic inflammation and the development of persistent microcirculatory disorders. In the immunopathogenesis of CGP, a significant role is assigned to processes accompanied by an autoimmune reaction against periodontal antigens. To date, numerous experimental data have been accumulated that allow us to talk about several important functions of the endothelium: its role in angiogenesis, lipoprotein metabolism, regulation of vascular tone and hemocoagulation potential of plasma blood.

Keywords: chronic generalized periodontitis, arterial hypertension, composition of saliva, endothelial dysfunction, endothelin, angiotensin.

**Давлатова Дилрабо,
Усманова Шоира**
Ташкентский Медицинский Академии
Ташкентский Государственный стоматологический институт
shoira.usmanova.1980@gmail.com

РОЛЬ ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛЬНОЙ ДИСФУНКЦИИ В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ПАРОДОНТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Многочисленными исследованиями доказано, что эндотелиальной дисфункция в тканях пародонта часто приводит к формированию хронического воспаления и развитию стойких микроциркуляторных нарушений. В иммунопатогенезе ХГП существенная роль отводится процессам, сопровождающимся аутоиммунной реакцией против антигенов пародонта. К настоящему времени накоплены многочисленные экспериментальные данные, позволяющие говорить о нескольких важнейших функциях эндотелия: его роли в ангиогенезе, метаболизме липопротеинов, регуляции сосудистого тонуса и гемокоагуляционного потенциала плазмы крови.

Ключевые слова: хронический генерализованный пародонтит, артериальная гипертензия, состав слюны, эндотелиальная дисфункция, эндотелин, ангиотензин.

Давлатова Дилрабо,
Усманова Шоира
Тошкент Тиббиёт Академия
Ташкент давлат стоматология институт
shoira.usmanova.1980@gmail.com

ЭНДОТЕЛИАЛ ДИСФУНКЦИЯНИНГ ЯЛЛИҒЛАНИШЛИ ПАРОДОНТ КАСАЛЛИКЛАР ПАТОГЕНЕЗИДАГИ РОЛИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Кўпгина тадқиқотлар пародонт тўқималарда эндотелиал дисфункция кўпинча сурункали яллиғланишнинг шаклланишига ва доимий микроциркуляцион касалликларнинг ривожланишига олиб келишини исботлади. СГП иммунопатогенезида пародонт антигенларга қарши аутоиммун реакция билан кечадиган жараёнлар муҳим рол ўйнайди. Бугунги кунга келиб, эндотелиянинг бир нечта муҳим функциялари ҳақида гапиришга имкон берадиган кўплаб экспериментал маълумотлар тўпланган: унинг ангиогенездаги роли, липопротеин метаболизми, қон томир тонусини тартибга солиш ва плазма қонининг гемокоагуляция салоҳияти.

Калит сўзлар: сурункали генераллашган пародонтит, артериал гипертензия, сўлак таркиби, эндотелиал дисфункция, эндотелин, ангиотензин.

Introduction. The reasons for the chronization of periodontal tissue inflammation are still poorly understood, which determines the low effectiveness of preventive and therapeutic measures. The accumulated data allow us to consider the multifactorial nature of chronic generalized periodontitis as the most likely.

The need to improve diagnostic criteria that allow separating the boundaries of useful adaptation of periodontal tissues from the beginning of the pathological process, as well as the establishment of specific mechanisms of the pathogenesis of CGP determine the relevance of this study.

The presence of common immunopathological processes in the pathogenesis of CGP and inflammatory diseases can be considered as another probable mechanism of the relationship between the formation of inflammatory-dystrophic changes in periodontal disease in patients with CGP. On the other hand, generalized degenerative-inflammatory lesions of the parotid tissues are an unsolved problem of practical dentistry. Local therapeutic measures in the oral cavity, as a rule, give a temporary effect and do not interfere with the progressive course of the disease, which convinces of the need to evaluate its pathogenesis from the standpoint of systemically acting mechanisms. The high prevalence of inflammatory periodontal diseases, the lack of methods of diagnosis and treatment of this pathology motivate the urgency of studying the problems of dental diseases. The urgency of the problem also determines the need for further studies of the mechanisms of atherogenesis, including in periodontal diseases. All of the above mechanisms are obligate pathogenetic links in periodontal pathology.

Saliva is used as a diagnostic substrate not only to reduce the cost of obtaining information compared to blood analysis, but also to collect data that is more difficult to obtain in the study of blood serum. Evaluation of the quality and quantity of saliva in general somatic pathology, accompanied by a violation of its secretion, allows us to predict the development of certain dental diseases (caries, periodontitis, sialadenitis, Gougereau-Sjogren, etc.). Using the information obtained during the study of saliva, conditions will be created for the disclosure of the pathogenesis and diagnosis of conditions and diseases necessary for their prevention and treatment.

A special place among the diseases associated with periodontitis is occupied by cardiovascular, endocrine, gastrointestinal diseases, as well as skeletal lesions. In recent years, numerous factors and pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of generalized periodontitis have been identified.

Endothelial dysfunction can be defined as inadequate formation of various biologically active substances in the endothelium (imbalance). The term "endothelial dysfunction" refers to many, often reversible changes in the functional status of the endothelium, which are a response to external stimuli. However, with prolonged exposure to damaging factors, a gradual disruption of the functioning of the endothelium occurs.

Material and methods. 65 people of both sexes aged 20 to 40 years (average age 35 years) were examined. All the study participants live in the territory of Uzbekistan. In women, the phase of the menstrual cycle was taken into account (studies were conducted in the first phase of the cycle). The choice of this age group was determined by the fact that the chronic course of periodontal diseases manifest in adulthood. In addition, by this time the dentition system and the entire complex of periodontal tissues have been fully formed.

The condition of periodontal tissues was assessed according to clinical methods, in which patients' complaints, anamnesis of the main disease, the presence of occupational hazards, concomitant diseases were clarified. During an objective examination, the dental formula was fixed, the CPI index was calculated, the bite condition, the attachment of the bridles, the condition of the gums (color, swelling, bleeding), the presence of soft and hard dental deposits, hyperesthesia of the hard tissues of the teeth were determined, pathological mobility of the teeth was determined taking into account 4 degrees.

To study the state of the bone tissue of the alveolar processes, an X-ray examination was performed. The hygienic condition of the oral cavity was determined by the OHI-S index (Green, Vermilion, 1960), periodontal tissue inflammation - papillary-marginal-alveolar turkey - PMA (RagmaS., 1960), IR - degree of bleeding according to H. Mullemann and S. Son (1971), PI - degree of destruction of noA. Russel (1956), the depth of periodontal pockets was measured (WHO, 1990). The clinical condition of periodontal tissues was assessed using the Schiller-Pisarev test.

Research results. The average value of index indicators indicates significant disorders in periodontal tissues: OHI-So evaluates the hygienic condition of the oral cavity as unsatisfactory, CPU characterizes the high prevalence of caries, PMA - characterizes the average degree of inflammation, significantly exceeds the norm, which indicates the destruction of periodontal tissues, IR - is quite high.

In order to objectify the assessment of the state of periodontal tissues in patients with chronic periodontitis of moderate severity, generally accepted index indicators were used, which included the PMA - papillary-marginal-alveolar index; API - index of the approximal surfaces; SBI - index of bleeding of the dentoalveolar furrow; PI - periodontal index.

Based on these data, diagnoses were made: chronic generalized periodontitis of moderate severity.

In order to objectify the assessment of the condition of periodontal tissues in patients with chronic periodontitis of moderate severity, generally accepted index indicators were used, which included the PMA - papillary-marginal-alveolar index; API - index of the approximal surfaces; SBI - index of bleeding of the dentoalveolar furrow; PI - periodontal index.

In the pathogenesis of microcirculation disorders in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis (CGP), an important role belongs to disorders in the vascular-platelet, coagulation links of the hemostasis system, as well as thromboresistance of the vascular wall endothelium. Disorders in the hemostasis system in this category of patients develop by the type of disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) of blood [9,10,11,12]. Since there are significant gaps in our knowledge of the pathogenesis of periodontal diseases, more fundamental and invasive research is needed. To solve this problem, we decided to evaluate the thrombogenic potential of blood in CGP. Thus, as a result of the conducted studies, it was found that in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis, there is a decrease in thrombosis resistance of the vascular wall, which is manifested by inhibition of anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity of the endothelium. Changes in vascular endothelial thrombosis resistance depend on the underlying disease, i.e. chronic generalized periodontitis. A decrease in the anticoagulant activity of the vascular endothelium in patients with periodontitis is manifested by inhibition of the release of antithrombin III by the vascular wall endothelium. Arginine- and lysine-

specific cysteine proteases of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* are known to cause degradation and inactivation of thrombomodulin in endothelial cells of gum microvessels in patients with periodontitis. At the same time, it is known that thrombomodulin binding thrombin causes changes in the conformation of its active center, resulting in an increased rate of inactivation of its antithrombin III. On the other hand, it was found that a number of inflammatory cytokines, in particular, interleukin 1, as well as tumor necrosis factor, cause a decrease in anticoagulant activity of the vascular wall endothelium. In this regard, it is most likely that in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis, the decrease in anticoagulant activity of the vascular wall endothelium is due both to the direct influence of periodontopathogenic microflora and indirectly to the action of immune mechanisms implemented in a long-existing focus of inflammation. The data obtained by us are presented in table III.2.1. indicates that in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis, there is an increase in the time of Hageman-dependent fibrinolysis and a decrease in the fibrinolytic activity of the vascular endothelium. Inhibition of fibrinolytic activity of the vascular endothelium in the combined form of the disease may be associated with a decrease in the release of tissue plasminogen activator t-PA. At the same time, there is evidence in the literature that the production of tissue plasminogen activator t-PA increases in patients with periodontitis, but at the same time the production of tissue plasminogen activator PAI-2 increases. As a result of the conducted studies, it was revealed that in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of moderate severity, there is an increase in the serum content of not only endothelin I, but also homocysteine, while the concentration of homocysteine in the blood serum is higher than in the group of healthy individuals. Homocysteine is a cytotoxic amino acid and its low content in cells is ensured: by remethylation to methionine and transulfation to cysteine. Remethylation of homocysteine to methionine is carried out in all cells of the body by the enzyme methionine synthetase, and vitamin B12 acts as a coenzyme. 5-methyltetrahydrofolate (5-MTHF), the active form of folic acid, is used as a donor of the methyl group necessary for the conversion of homocysteine to methionine. In the process of transulfation, the enzyme cystathionine- β -synthetase catalyzes the conversion of homocysteine and serine into cystathionine, which then undergoes hydrolysis to form cysteine and α -ketobutyrate under the influence of the enzyme cystathionase. At the same time, vitamin B6 is used as a coenzyme in both reactions. In case of violation of intracellular metabolism of homocysteine, "extra" homocysteine is excreted from the cell into the extracellular space and further into the blood. This leads to hyperhomocysteinemia and, consequently, toxic effects on endothelial cells. It is known that with periodontitis, numerous metabolic disorders occur in periodontal tissues. Thus, a change in bacterial phagocytosis by polymorphonuclear leukocytes in combination with a delay in neutrophil apoptosis is accompanied by their hyperproduction of reactive oxygen species, which aggravates the course of the pathological process. In periodontal tissues, the intensity of free radical oxidation increases, the number of SH-groups decreases, which leads to significant damage to cell membranes. Hyperhomocysteinemia, detected in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis, is probably a consequence of metabolic disorders and, above all, lipid peroxidation in periodontal tissues. In the blood, homocysteine can undergo an oxidation process, as a result of which the superoxide anion and other free radicals that damage the endothelium are released. The result of the damaging effect of homocysteine is the development of endothelial dysfunction, which is accompanied by a change in the production of a number of regulatory substances produced by the endothelium, in particular, a decrease in the synthesis of nitric oxide and prostacyclin and an increase in the formation of thromboxanes (...). It is known that homocysteine reduces the anticoagulant activity of the vascular wall endothelium, due to the degradation of thrombomodulin, a decrease in the expression of antithrombin III-heparin complexes on the surface of endothelial cells and significantly reduces the activity of the protein C system. In addition, homocysteine causes a decrease in plasminogen activation, due to stimulation of a thrombin-activated fibrinolysis inhibitor - TAFI (thrombin-activatable fibrinolysis inhibitor). It is important to note that homocysteine increases the expression of the plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1) gene, which suppresses fibrinolysis

Conclusion. In patients with CGP, it is accompanied not only by metabolic disorders on the part of periodontal tissues, but also by serious deviations in the physico-chemical parameters of the

oral fluid, which is manifested by microcirculatory disorders caused by increased platelet aggregation activity and an imbalance of markers of endothelial dysfunction. Endothelial dysfunction in periodontitis is not limited only to the microcirculatory bed of periodontal tissues, but is systemic in nature

In patients with CGP, there was a violation of thromboresistance of the vascular wall, where violations of both anticoagulant and fibrinolytic activity of the vascular endothelium predominate.

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